

VIEWING COMPREHENSION PERFORMANCE OF THE 7TH GRADER STUDENTS IN A RURAL HIGH SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

The study determined the viewing comprehension performance of the 7th grader students of San Juan National High School. The study used Single Subject Experimental Design and the respondents were the grade 7 learners. There were 10 respondents (5 male & 5 female) in every average standard score – below average, average, above average. The researcher consulted 3 experts to evaluate their answers. The findings revealed that the viewing comprehension performance of the students with the five different genres was most of the students clearly adhere the ambition genre which was constantly at the high score from before viewing to extended. In addition, there was significant increase in the viewing comprehension performance of the students from before viewing to extended and there was significant difference on viewing comprehension performance of the students according to sex and academic performance. Viewing Comprehension Performance was based on the presentation of pictures and short videos followed by 5 comprehension questions in every structure. The researcher suggested to use this Viewing Comprehension Strategies to enhance the viewing comprehension performance of the students. In connection with this, the researcher made workbook that can help students to hone their language skills.

Key Words: *Viewing Comprehension, Viewing Comprehension Performance*

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The breakthrough of technology has come with the fifth macro skills which is viewing in addition to listening, speaking, reading and writing. Since viewing skills have become part of the learning process and important means of communication especially in this 21st century, students rely much on viewing. In this connection, the study claims that viewing comprehension can improve the performance of the students.

Student's viewing play a vital role in the retention of knowledge. According to Estroga (2012), viewing enhances both reading and listening skills when students attend to non-verbal communication and visual elements of performance, video, television, film, multimedia presentation and visual accompanying print, specific textual techniques, and the assumptions, perspectives and quality of a variety media. Moreover, Isidor (2014) added that students take in information 55 percent in visual and only 7 percent in text. In that case, Shea in 2014 reported that video was especially effective for low-achievement students since it enabled them to match learning pace with their own needs. It also accounted for increased student motivation and generate positive affective outcomes for all kinds of video use. This, in turn, led to improved grades and motivation. Fisch (2017) with his study *“Bridging theory and practice: applying cognitive and educational theory to the design of educational media”* theorized that certain viewer characteristics, including prior knowledge and high working-memory capacity, help children learn from educational media. Students can vary in their abilities to interpret visuals, Lin (2009).

In San Juan National High School, San Juan, Southern Leyte, the researcher observed that some Grade 7 students were low in comprehension level based on the Phil- Iri assessment results from pre to post tests. . Even though they are now at the secondary level, they find it tough to comprehend what they have read especially those scenes requiring higher order thinking skills. With the recent integration of viewing as a macro skill in language learning simultaneous with the implementation of the K to 12 from school year 2013-2014 added with the proliferation of multimedia technology, the challenge to guide the students to select, validate, and interpret these visual images were among the many arduous tasks teachers have to face and successfully accomplish. For this reason, educators should not focus only on the listening, speaking, reading and writing skills of the students but also to their viewing skill for they belong to 21st century of learners. As students view visual messages, they need to activate and even further their comprehension performance level by giving strategies to make sense of the visual images accompanied with oral and print languages.

This embarked the researcher to determine the viewing comprehension performance of the 7th Grader in a rural high school using the viewing comprehension strategy. The researcher designed a self-developed instructional module to enhance learners viewing comprehension performance level.

Significance of the Study

The findings of the study serve as an input to the curriculum makers, school administrators, teachers, students, parents and the community to consider the applied viewing comprehension strategy, as a tool to promote high quality education in the 21st century for all students, and for the community as well as to the educators who are willing to adopt the strategy for any educational enhancement. Most importantly, this assists English teachers to consider the latter as a possible breakthrough in their teaching strategy for higher academic performance.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the viewing comprehension performance of the 7th Grader students in San Juan National High School.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the viewing comprehension level of the 7th graders according to sex and academic performance and viewing comprehension strategy?
2. Is there a significant increase in the viewing comprehension performance of the respondents from before viewing to extended viewing?
3. Is there a significant difference in the viewing comprehension performance of the students according to sex, academic and viewing comprehension strategy applied?

Summary of Related Literature

Viewing Comprehension Kit, a school-based teacher – made intervention-strategy is patterned on Terry Heick (2019) Viewing Comprehension Strategies: Watching Videos like reading a book. This aims to bolster the reading comprehension skills of learners, and address the gap of understanding the content of the texts among learners of San Juan National High School. The Viewing Comprehension Lesson is laddered using the four fundamental structures; Before-During-After-Extended structures with five (5) literary genres: Disaster, Justice, Love, Ambition and Looking Back based on the Grade 7 learning material.

Each structure has four anchored strategies. These are "thinking templates" used in multiple contexts and combinations. As with reading strategies, there was overlap from one part to another. That is, some strategies can be utilized in countless ways. These anchored strategies are the most universal, and thus the most flexible for use with different kinds of videos, in different content areas, and at different index of difficulty. Questions under each ladder are categorized as Below Average, Average and Above Average.

In addition, it uses specific strategy in each structure. In before viewing, it uses the *connect strategy*. In during viewing, it uses the *infer strategy*. In after viewing, it uses the *analyze strategy*. Lastly, extended viewing uses *create and reflect strategy*.

The intervention will be adapted as a strategic intervention to improve their reading and develop comprehension skills of the Grade 7 learners.

This adapted intervention will be introduced as an approach to assist learners in understanding the video materials in different genres of English 7 and will be integrated as one of the major activities to aid their comprehension.

METHODOLOGY

This chapter describes how the study is conducted, the research design used in the study, the research locale, the participants of the study, the research procedures, the research instrument and statistical treatment used in the study.

Research Design

This study employed a single subject experimental design. This is the use of the very subject (student) as his own control by changing the intervention treatment presented to the student and carefully assessing via repeated observations or measurements, the impact of the changes in the experimental treatment on the subject as he exhibits certain new behavior a number of times under the various treatment conditions. This was utilized in the study by having a particular group of learners were being exposed to the viewing comprehension questions (Kpolovie, 2016). This design was appropriate in dealing with the results of the students on their viewing comprehension as to their progress from module 1 down to module 5 from before viewing to extended viewing. The design best fits this study as it aimed to developed instructional module for viewing comprehension. Since this design deals with experimentation with one subject by subjecting a student to detailed examinations for certain practical evaluation and determination of the effects of the experimental treatment conditions on the student. In this manner, this research design is successfully used to investigate and scrutinize pure cause and effect relationships. In so saying, the intervention through the use of varied activities under viewing comprehension would effect into new changes or development of the learners.

The GPA of the students was also utilized in this study to divide the entire population into different subgroups namely below average, average and above average.

Research Environment

The study was conducted in San Juan National High School (SJNHS), San Jose, San Juan, Southern Leyte. At present this is the only secondary school in the municipality with 53 model teachers (45 Junior High School and 8 Senior High School teachers); one head teacher; and 4 non-teaching staffs. This school was established on April 27, 1997, by the virtue of the power granted by the Secretary of the Department of Education. After four years of operation, it had been registered under R.A. 9109 on April 14, 2001.

SJNHS has a total land area of 1.5 hectares donated by the San Juan Polytechnic College permitted by the Commission on Higher Education through their Campus

Administrator, who then donated the one-hectare lot to the Local Government of San Juan and donated it to the Department of Education in February 4, 1997. The same institution donated the additional 0.5-hectare through a MOA between the Department of Education and the Southern Leyte State College of Science and Technology, which was approved in February 14, 2002.

Research Respondents and Sampling Procedure

The sample respondents of the study were thirty (30) Grade 7 students who were presently enrolled in San Juan National High School, San Jose, San Juan, Southern Leyte for the school year 2017-2018. Grade 7 has seven sections and three sections were handled by the researcher- Rizal, Mabini, and Jacinto. The study focused on one set of a section and the researcher chose section Rizal as the respondents of the study. To determine the respondents, the researcher used the General Percentage Average (GPA) in computing the second grading grades in English of the students because there is no other measure to compare the equivalence of performance of the respondents.

Stratified Sampling Technique was used in one section wherein the entire population were divided into strata namely below average, average and above average.

Research Instrument

This study utilized questionnaires specially crafted and validated by experts for viewing comprehension purposes aligned with the Barrett's Taxonomy Levels of Viewing Comprehension. Visual images used include pictures and videos. The viewing comprehension questionnaires were divided equally fitting to the 3 groups of respondents namely: below average, average and above average. Each group is tasked to answer 5 modules which are grouped from easy to difficult levels and with activities ranging from before viewing down to extended viewing. Students under the below average level are to do the easy modules, while the average students are to work on the average questions , and the difficult tasks in the modules are for those students belonging to the above average level. It is a pre-requisite for each student to finish first the first module before proceeding to the next one. Technically, these questions in each set have 5 items following the higher order thinking skills format following the competencies and texts from Grade 7 learning materials under the Kto12 program.

There were five (5) videos of different genres being used in this study. This include disaster, justice, love, ambition and looking back. Each genre has a corresponding video. 2012 film by Ronal Emmerich for disaster theme, My Father Goes to Court by Carlos Bolusan for justice, Footnote to Youth by Jose Garcia- Villa for love, Bread of Salt by NVM Gonzales for ambition; and Where's the Patis? By Carmen Guerrero- Nakpil for the theme looking back.

Rubrics were also visible for the extended viewing activity for the students to be guided on the tasks given to them.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher asked permission from the school head/principal to conduct the study at San Juan National High School. A letter of consent was given and answered by the respondents as evidence that they were permitted to engage in the study and obeyed to the terms and conditions laid on the permit.

To determine the viewing comprehension performance of the respondents according to sex, academic performance and viewing comprehension strategy applied, the researcher used the General Percentage Average (GPA) to carefully select 30 students as respondents of the study. This 30 students were equally divided having 5 females & 5 males for the above average, another sets for the average as well as the above average levels specifically from one section. They were exposed to the videos as tools for the viewing comprehension strategy.

The viewing comprehension strategies were used to the respondents during 15 school days in one hour. There had 3 days for each video. During the implementation of the strategies, teacher-made questions were raised from before viewing to extended to check the comprehension of the students. The researcher used one anchor strategy from each structure. For before viewing, the researcher used connect strategy. For during viewing, the researcher used infer strategy. For after viewing, the researcher used analyze strategy. For extended, the researcher used reflect strategy. The respondents answered the viewing comprehension questions in order for the researcher to gather the necessary data on the viewing comprehension during the implementation of the study. The answer of the students in viewing comprehension questions were automatically recorded on an individual basis. A holistic rubric was used to determine the viewing comprehension performance of the respondents according to sex, academic performance and viewing comprehension strategy applied.

The objective of this was to determine the viewing comprehension performance and viewing comprehension strategy applied that in the study. The results were collected, analyzed and tabulated.

After the respondents answered the comprehension questions, the researcher gathered them and submitted to the 3 experts to evaluate and gave the accurate score based on the rubrics.

The three (3) experts were DepEd Secondary English teachers, 2 master's degree holder and 1 having doctoral units in PhD-English (CAR).

The viewing comprehension study was used every Wednesday to Friday from January to February 2018 during their Remedial Reinforcement and Enhancement (RRE). Below is the Ghannt Chart.

GANTT CHART

Schedule Date Every Wednesday- Friday (January 10 – February 9, 2018)	January 10-12, 2018	January 17-19, 2018	January 24-26, 2018	January 31- February 2, 2018	February 7-9, 2018
Video/Topic	2012	Footnote to Youth	My Father Goes to Court	Bread of Salt	Where is the Patis?

Data Analysis

The data were collected, tallied and analyzed using the following statistical tools:

T-test was used to identify the increase in the viewing comprehension performance according to sex, academic performance and viewing comprehension strategy applied.

Anova was used to test the difference on the viewing comprehension according to the sex, academic performance and viewing comprehension strategy applied.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the findings, analysis and interpretation of data gathered in which the main objective is to determine the viewing comprehension performance of the 7th grader students.

Viewing Comprehension Performance

Figure 1. Before Viewing Comprehension Performance with Five Different Video Genre

The data presented in figure 1 shows the academic performance on before viewing comprehension. It clearly indicated that most of the below average students were in the literal level. The below average male students got high score in love and looking back video genre. Most of the below average female students got high score in reorganization level but some of them were in literal level. The average male students got perfect score in reorganization level. The average female students also got most in reorganization level but only few got score in inferential level. The above average female students got perfect score in inferential level. Most of the above average male students got high score in inferential level but few of them were in reorganizational level.

According to (Estroga, 2012), students can learn to “read” the pictures, the diagram and the table, maps and charts. These skills would provide them with increased information about the material. Most of the students from below average to above average got the perfect score from the genre ambitions, this indicated that their level at young age were more likely on ambitions. This result testified from the study of (Barsukova, 2017), 72 % students considered themselves ambitious. From the study of Judge and (Mueller, 2019) there were positive life outcomes of ambition. Participants who were more ambitious did not appear to be made miserable or insatiable by their ambitions. Instead, they found that individuals who were more ambitious had higher levels of attainment in both education and work aspects.

Figure 2. During Viewing Comprehension Performance with Five Different Video Genre

The figure 2 shows the academic performance on during viewing comprehension. Based from the presentation, all below average students were in the reorganization level while the above average got perfect score in inferential level. On the other hand, some of the average students were in the reorganization level but most of them were in inferential level. According to the English Language Arts (2007) as cited by Isidor (2014), students encounter thoughts, ideas by viewing, as well as listening and reading. By this, students should give opportunities to view a variety of formats including visuals, drama and media.

Figure 3. After Viewing Comprehension Performance with Five Different Video Genre

The after viewing comprehension figure 3 shows that the students under the above average got the highest level of comprehension which was evaluation and appreciation while the average were in the inferential level of comprehension. In the below average, only male students got few in reorganization level but most of them were in the inferential level. Students can vary in their abilities to interpret visuals, Heinich et al., (2009). Some students can successfully understand the content of video segments whereas others may confront comprehension failures. To have a significant improvement in understanding the video, the students' needs to learn the expertise of video comprehension strategies.

Figure 4. Extended Viewing Comprehension Performance with Five Different Video Genre

In the extended, figure 4 shows that both average and above average students were in the level of evaluation and appreciation while most of the male and female below average were in the level of evaluation and appreciation but few were in the inferential level. A positive effect can be observed in the study regarding the performance of the students on the extended wherein most of the students clearly understand the concept of the videos. This result, that the presence of new technology and new means of using it entail the development of new models, the addition of multimedia capabilities imply the whole new set of pedagogical models. The use of audio and video in language instruction to ground our models of good practice in the areas of multimedia and in the language learning, Hoven (2012). As a researcher, we should look and explore the students their relationship with newer technology with a view toward developing a sociocultural language learning model that incorporate these features.

Significant Increase in the Viewing Comprehension Performance of the Respondents from Before Viewing to Extended Viewing

Figure 5. Increase in the viewing comprehension performance of the respondents from before viewing to extended viewing

This figure 5 shows the increase in the viewing comprehension performance of the respondents from before viewing to extended. It's like a ladder which showcase the results from before viewing (m=6.726), during viewing (m=8.216), after viewing (m=10.358), and extended (m=12.6873). The comprehension level of the students has a positive result, and develop more and more through the use of viewing comprehension, as we can observed the results from the before viewing and its different from other level. This result proves the idea from (Mayer, 2008).

It's clearly, we want to incorporate multimedia learning and use it most effectively, simply because multimedia learning incorporates words and pictures, it can be a chapter in a textbook that includes pictures or charts. It can also be online lesson that incorporate videos. Research has found out that average of 6-7 hours a day using media (video games, computers, video), with the average television viewing at 3-4 hours each day. This made some research body suggest to teach children to become critical viewers, give them the ability to analyze the construction of isolated images, give them the ability to

think critically about the composition of the picture and enhance their ability to read word and worlds (Considine & Moorman, 2009).

Figure 6. Significant difference of the mean score

This figure 6 shows the significant difference of the viewing comprehension performance from before viewing to extended viewing. The interval did not contain zero, the corresponding means were significantly different. In every structure of viewing were significantly difference to each other as shown in the figure. For before to after viewing the interval was in between the mean score of -4.10188 and -3.16212. For during to after viewing the interval was in between the mean score of -2.61188 and -1.67212. For extended to after viewing the interval was in between the mean score of 1.85945 and 2.79921. For during down to before viewing activity, the interval was in between the mean score of 1.02012 and 1.95988. For extended down to before viewing the interval was in between the mean score of 5.49145 and 6.43121. For extended to during viewing the interval was in between the mean score of 4.00145 and 4.94121. The viewing comprehension structure, the stimulus was a short video. Subsequent to the video presentation, multiple-choice questions are prompted asking for detailed information or conclusions that can be drawn out of the previously presented video. In order to respond correctly, first, auditory and visual information has to be extracted from the video. After gathering pieces of information, the next process in the chain is relating the pieces to each other and connecting them with already stored knowledge in a mental model of the video sequence (Bucholtz, 2010).

Significant Difference on Viewing Comprehension Performance According to Sex and Academic Performance

Figure 7. Interval Plot of Score vs Recoded Sex

This figure 7 shows the interval plot of score of male and female. As you can see the interval plot of score of male has $m=9.35067$ while female has $m=9.643$. It shows that the female got the highest score than male. Men and women had a number of differences in some ways (Lakoff, 1973 & Haas, 1979). Researchers have long agreed girls have superior language abilities to boys, but haven't clearly provided a biological basis to account for their differences. For the first time and in unambiguous findings, researchers show both that brain areas associated with language tasks, and that boys and girls rely on very different parts of the brain when performing these tasks. Language processing is more abstract in girls, more sensory in boys, Burman (2008).

In addition, the researcher found out that girls still showed significantly greater activation in language areas of the brain than boys. Holmes in Wardhaugh (2006) offers some testable claims about gender differences in using language. Those cover men and women develop different patterns of using language, women usually focus on the affective functions of an interaction more often than men do, women tend to use linguistic devices that stress solidarity more often than men do, women usually communicate in some ways which will maintain and increase solidarity while men tend to communicate in some ways which will focus on the power and status and women are stylistically more flexible than men.

Figure 8. Significant difference of means score according to sex

This figure 8 shows the significant difference of the viewing comprehension performance according to sex. The interval did contain zero, the corresponding means were not significantly different of female to male respondents as shown in the figure. The female to male respondents got the mean score of 0.3. In Lin's (2011) study, there was no significant difference between males and females' video comprehension test scores on a challenging videotext. According to him, the data indicated that the acquisition of vocabulary and the growth of second language comprehension skills depended on the degree of text difficulty. The tasks of understanding videotexts and learning vocabulary generally showed gender differences. The performances of both genders when seeing a challenging videotext are practically equal. The author's findings from earlier studies can be used to explain this result (Lin, 2009). It sums up that both genders can comprehend the video they watched depend on what skills they are good at.

Figure 9. Interval Plot of Score vs Recoded Academic Performance

This figure 9 shows the interval plot of score versus the academic performance. It shows ladder interval of academic performance from below average to above average. In the context of literacy instruction, the study of McIntyre (2011) revealed that literacy instruction can be delivered more effectively with the aid of technology. Because technology has redefined visual literacy, Dyck (2010) as mentioned in the study of Gabinete (2016) believes that educators should seek resources from Hollywood movies, that movies are instrumental in shaping young learners' minds in critical way. That is why there is positive result of viewing comprehension performance according to academic performance of the learners. However, teachers need to have knowledge of how to express ideas and emotions visually.

Figure 10. Significant Difference of Means Score according to Academic Performance

This figure 10 shows the significant difference of the viewing comprehension according to academic performance. The interval did not contain zero, the corresponding means were significantly different. For average to below average, the interval was in between the mean score of 1.5 and 2.5. For above average to below average, the interval was in between the mean score of 3.1 and 4.5. Lastly, the interval in above average to average was in between the mean score of 1.1 and 2.2. Academic performance has been the subject of multiple recent studies. Overall, as summarized by (Lamas, 2015) performance can be understood as the result of multiple interactions between several factors, including school characteristics, physical and pedagogic aspects, teacher qualifications, family attributes like parental style and education level, and individual characteristics such as physical health, motivation to learn, emotional factors and cognitive development.

The results indicated that students' viewing comprehension using the Barrett's Taxonomy of levels of comprehension and the viewing comprehension structures with indicated strategies positively affected the viewing comprehension performance of the students. In addition, the results indicate that there is a significant increase in the viewing comprehension performance of the respondents according to sex, academic performance and viewing comprehension strategies applied and significant difference in the viewing comprehension performance of the students according to sex, academic and viewing comprehension strategy applied.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The learning preferences or habits may be crucial factors for determining the successful utilization of video. Less organized learners may benefit more from video than

their more highly organized counterparts. However, this conclusion needs to be verified using a much larger sample.

2. Some apparent advantages of video were disadvantages for some students. First, although video affords self-paced studying, some students found that pausing the lecture disrupted the context, even for short pauses. Regaining context in a video mode is much more difficult than in a textual one because, in the latter, many visual cues help retrieve context. With video, context retrieval, involving rewinding and re playing, sometimes caused frustration.

3. To the best of our knowledge, relationships between students' approaches to studying (deep or surface level orientations) and specific instructional media have not been investigated. Findings from this study enabled us to make a tentative hypothesis regarding the issue. It seems that students who use a surface approach to study would be frustrated since the medium makes such an approach difficult. That is, reproducing text from video requires transcribing the lectures, a step that is unnecessary with text.

4. The self-developed module for Grade 7 English students is useful as a supplementary material in improving students' viewing comprehension performance.

Recommendations

Based on the above summary of findings and conclusion, it is recommended that:

1. A workbook in viewing comprehension for grade 7 students is to be utilized as a supplemental material in improving learner's viewing comprehension performance.
2. Viewing materials such as pictures, videos or any supplemental materials are to be used in teaching the viewing comprehension performance.
3. Strategies and activities for viewing comprehension should be authentic and relevant to their level to facilitate schema of learning.
4. Learning materials such as workbooks and other supplemental materials needs to be provided to the learners to facilitate and improve acquisition of language skills.
5. New innovative methods of viewing comprehension teaching need to be used in teaching K to 12 curriculum.
6. A pre and post-test is to be done to measure their viewing comprehension before and after they answer the workbook or any supplemental materials for viewing comprehension.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This is a declaration by the author that informed consent was obtained, the respondents were free to withdraw from the study at any time, anonymity of the respondents was maintained, the respondents' well-being was safeguarded, no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research.

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